

A case study of Ayurvedic management of Kitibha Kushtha with special reference to Palmoplantar Psoriasis

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Abstract

People suffering from Autoimmune diseases is increasing day by day. The exact cause of the autoimmune disease is still unknown. Psoriasis is one such disease. Dry thick raised itchy patches on the skin are the sign of Psoriasis. They are covered with silvery-white scales. It is triggered by infection stress and cold. Psoriasis is one of the most common clinical conditions encountered in clinical practice majority of the dermatological disorders have described under the roof of *Kushtha* in *Ayurveda* *Kitibha* is a type of *Kshudra Kushtha* described in different *Ayurvedic* classics is *Vata-Kaphaja* the clinical symptoms of *Kitibha* described in *Ayurveda* resembles with symptoms of Psoriasis the current treatment modalities have their own limitations and the drugs have considerable side effects when using for longer period. According to *Ayurveda* Psoriasis is treated with both *Shodhana* and *Shamana Chikitsa*. It affects almost 2% worldwide population. The high chances of recurrence and its reluctant nature makes it a matter of concern for modern medicine as they have a limited line of treatment. including *Snehpana*, *Vamana*, *Virechana* and *Raktaamokshna* etc.

Keywords: *Kitibha*; *Kshutha*; *Shodhana*; *Snehpana*; *Vamana*; *Virechana*; *Raktaamokshna*.

1. Introduction

Psoriasis is a common, chronic, non-communicable skin disease with no clear cause or cure. Skin is the mirror which reflects the harmony of internal functions of the body. Any change in skin color disturbs the patient both mentally and physically. The negative impact of this condition on people's lives can be immense. Psoriasis affects people of all ages, and in all countries. It is uncommon under the age of 5 years. More than 50% of patients present before the age of 30 years. The reported prevalence of Psoriasis in countries ranges between 0.09% and 11.43%.^[1]

Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory, hyper-proliferative skin disease. it is characterized by well defined, erythematous scaly plaques, particularly affecting extensor surface, scalp and nails and usually follows relapsing remitting course.^[2] It is a common dermatologic disease, affecting up to 1% of the World's population.^[3]

The word Psoriasis is derived from Greek word 'Psora' means 'itch' and 'sis' meaning 'acting condition'. In Psoriasis, main abnormality is of increased epidermal proliferation due to excessive multiplication of cells in the basal layers. The transit time of keratinocyte is shortened and epidermal turnover is reduced to 5-6 days from 28-30 days.^[4] Even though the etiology is unknown, the factors involved are genetic, biochemical and immuno-pathological.^[5]

Precipitating factors like trauma, infections, sunlight, some drugs and emotions may flare up.

Kitibha Kushtha manifests due aggravation of *Tridosha* especially dominance of *Vata* and *Kapha*.^[6] *Mithya Ahara* and *Vihara* vitiate *Tridosha* which further lead to the affliction and aggravation of *Rasa*, *Rakta* *Mamsa* and *Lasika*.

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Predominance of *Vata* can be elicited with symptoms like blackish discoloration hardness, dryness and roughness to touch. *Kaphaa* predominance can be appreciated with the presence of severe itching as a cardinal symptom.

Vitiating of *Tridosha* followed by affliction of four entities viz. *Twaka*, *Raktaa*, *Mamsa* and *Lasika* leads to *Kushtha*. These seven are called as the seven morbid factors

(*Sapta-Dravya-Sangraha*) of *Kushtha*^[7]. No *Kushtha* manifests itself due to the aggravation of only on *Dosha*^[8]. Modern medical science treats Psoriasis with Puva, Retinoids, Methotrexate and Cyclosporine and Corticosteroids. But the disease recurrence and gives serious side effects like liver, kidney failure and bone marrow depletion. Hence *Ayurveda* plays important role. Present study is undertaken to provide safe and effective remedy for Psoriasis.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Case study

A 40 years male patient approached in *Kayachikitsa* O.P.D. presenting with the following complaints,

- *Ubhaya Hast Pradeshi-Twaka Vaivarnya, Kandu*
- *Ubhaya Pad Pradeshi - Twaka Daran, Kandu Shoola, Shweta Strav* and intermittently *Raktaastrav*.
- *Ubhay Ansa Sandhi* (Shoulder Joints), *Karpur Sandhi* (Wrist) *Pradeshi - Shoola Vama* (left) more than *Dakshin* (Right).
- *Nidranasha* (Insomnia).

All symptoms occurred since 4-5 years.

2.2. Past History

Patient was all right before 4-5 years. Then blackish discoloration, itching, dryness occurred on the skin of both palms, both legs sole. He was diagnosed as Psoriasis. He had taken Allopathic and Homeopathic treatment for same complaints. There was recurrence in his complaints. Hence, he came to *Kayachikitsa* O.P.D. for treatment

History: No history of any previous surgical or medical illness.

Allergy: No any drug/food allergy.

Family History: Not specific.

2.3. Examination

Pulse - 80/min
BP - 110/70 mm of Hg
RS - B/L Clear
CVS - S1 S2 Normal
CNS - Conscious Oriented
P/A - Soft

2.4. Ashtavidha Pariksha

Sparsha - Ruksha
Kshudha - Mandya
Mala - Asamyak
Shabda - Spashta
Akruti-Sthoola
Jivha - Sama
Druka - Prakrut

Table 1 *Shamanaa Chikitsa*

Date	Symptoms	Treatment Given
25/03/2021	<i>Tawaka Vaivarniya - Ubhaya Hastpad Pradeshi</i> <i>Kandu - Ubhaya Hastpada Pradeshi</i> <i>Twakaa Darana, Shoola – Ubhaya Hastpada Pradeshi</i> <i>Shoola - Ubhaya Ansa Sandhi Pradeshi.</i>	<i>Swayambhu</i> <i>Guggul 500 mg TDS</i> <i>Arogyavardhini Vati 500 mg TDS</i> <i>Mahamanjishtadi Kwatha 20 ml BD</i> <i>Aragwadh Kapila Vati 4 Tablets HS</i> <i>Shodhana Tail + Bhimseni Kapur -Kandu Pradeshi</i>
2/04/2021	<i>Kandu decrease</i> <i>Jalwat strav Raktaa strav</i> <i>20% Upshaya</i>	Same as above with <i>Rasamanikya Rasa 30 mg + Chopchini Churna +</i> <i>Yashtimadhu Churna + Vidanga (500 mg) each</i> <i>Anupana Goghrit</i>
12/04/2021	<i>Kandu, strav decrease, Ubhaya hastpada predeshi Vaivarnya, Sarva Sandhishoola</i> <i>25% Upshaya</i>	Same as above except <i>Arogyawardhini Vati</i>
10/05/2021	<i>Ubhay padpradeshi Krushna, Shwetavarni</i> <i>Twaka Vaivarnya , Twakarukshata</i> <i>30% Upshaya</i>	<i>Gandhak Rasayana 500 mg 2 TDS</i> <i>Sukshma Triphala Vati 500 mg 2 TDS</i> <i>Rasaapachaka Vati 500 mg 2 TDS</i> <i>Mahamanjishthadi Kwatha 20 ml BD</i> <i>Rasaamanikya Rasa (30mg) + Chopchini Churna +</i> <i>Yashtimadhu Churna + Vidanga Churna + Nimba</i> <i>Churna + Sariva Churna + (500 mg) each</i> <i>Anupana- Goghrit</i> <i>Shatdhaut Ghruta for local application</i>
15/06/2021	<i>75% Upshaya decrease in all symptoms</i>	Same as above <i>Amalki Mashi 1 gm BD, Anupana - Madhu</i>

Shodhana Chikitsa: - *Shodhana Chikitsa* was given by *Raktaamokshana* through leech therapy. Leech therapy was given twice a month to both upper and lower limb two leeches were applied. Patient was relieved and improved clinically up to 70% in all the symptoms.

Pathya: Avoid oily, spicy, junk, food, bakery.

3. Mode of action

Table 2 Mode of action of drugs

Drug	Action	Effect
<i>Arogyavardhini Vati</i>	<i>Kleda Shamanaa & pacify Tridosha</i>	<i>Kushthaghna</i>
<i>Shodhana Tail</i>	<i>Raktaa - Mamsagat Kleda Shoshana by Tikta, Ruksha Guna</i>	<i>Twakaroghna</i>
<i>Aragwadha Churna</i>	<i>Reduces Raktaagata Vata - Pitta</i>	<i>Raktaashuddhikara</i>
<i>Vidanga</i>	<i>Reduces Twaka Dushti</i>	<i>Kushthaghan, Krumighna, Raktaashuddhikara</i>
<i>Sariva</i>	<i>Rasa - Raktaagat Vata Pitta Shamana</i>	<i>Daha Shamana</i>
<i>Karpur</i>	<i>Dilate Blood vessels</i>	<i>Kandughna ,swedjanana</i>

<i>Mahamanjishthadi Kwatha</i>	<i>Raktaagata Kaphaa -Pitta Pachan,& Shamana by Tikta ,Kashay, Madhura Rasa & Ruksha Guna</i>	<i>Raktaaprasadana</i>
<i>Rasaamanikya</i>	<i>Tridoshaghan by Snidha, Guru Guna</i>	<i>Kushthaghna</i>
<i>Gandhak Rasayana</i>	<i>Raktaagata Pitta -Kaphaa Shamana</i>	<i>Raktaaprasadnan, Dahashamak ,Rasayana Kushthaghna</i>
<i>Nimba</i>	<i>Raktaa -mamsgat kleda Shodhana by Tikta ,Ruksha guna</i>	<i>Raktaashuddhikar</i>
<i>Chopchini</i>	<i>Rakta, Kapha, Vataghan</i>	<i>Raktaashuddikar</i>
<i>Yashtimadhu</i>	<i>Rakta, Kapha, Vataghan</i>	<i>Shonitshtapan, Raktaapittaghna</i>
<i>Sookshm Triphala</i>	<i>Tridoshahar + Raktashudhikar</i>	<i>Raktaashodhak</i>
<i>Swayambhuv Guggul</i>	<i>Kapha - Vata Shamana then Shoola Shamana</i>	<i>Kushthaghna, Shwitraghna</i>

4. Discussion

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Figure 1 Palm region Psoriasis before and after treatment

Figure 2 Sole region Psoriasis before and after treatment

- *Arogyavardhini Vati*: - *Kushtha Vyadhi* vitiates *Tridoshas* and then *Twaka, Mansa, Rakta* and *Lasika (Dravyasangrahsaptak)*. As we see from modern pathophysiological aspect, *Kushtha* is mainly caused due to *Grahani Vikruti*. Due to malfunctioning of *Grahani*, *Malavrodha* happens. *Vata Dosha* between the *Grahani* and *Pakwashaya* vitiates due to that *Malavrodha* and overall prokinetic and propulsive action of *Grahani* becomes defective. Due to this, some organic toxins formed and get absorbed resulting in *Dhatu Dushti* and finally *Kushtha Vyadhi*. *Arogyavardhini* overall works on functioning of *Grahani* and *Pakwashaya* and makes it [9] smooth and fine."
- *Aragwadha*: -*Charak* has described *Aragwadha* in *Kushthaghna* and *Kandughna Mahakashaya*. *Aragwadha* has good *Anulomaka* activity. *Kushtha* is *Rakta Pradoshaja Vyadhi*. *Pitta* and *Rakta* lives in association. So by doing *Pitta Anuloman*, *Aragwadha* indirectly dose *Raktadosha Shamana*.
- *Jatamansi*: -*Charak* has described *Jatamansi* in *Kandughna (Anti-pruritic) Mahakashaya*. As *Jatamansi* does *Vata Shamana* by *Snigdha Guna* and *Kapha Shamana* by *Tikta Kashaya Rasa*."
- *Vidanga*: -In *Kitibha Kushtha*, there is vitiation of *Kapha and Pitta Doshas*. *Vidanga* has *Ushna Veerya* and therefore acts as good *Kapha Vatashamak*. *Vidanga* acts as *Krumighna* by its *Prabhav*. *Charak* has described *Vidanga* in *Kushthaghna Mahakashay*^[12] (*Antidermatotic*). "All types of *Kushtha Vyadhi* are caused due to Vitiation of one of the *Tridosha* or due to *Krumi. Dosha* which vitiates heavily, dominates in *Kushtha*^[13]
- *Nimb*: -*Charak* also described *Nimb* in *Kandughna (Anti-pruritic) Mahakashaya*. *Nimb* acts as *Kapha Vatashamak* by its *Tikta Kashay Rasa*, and also acts as very good *Krumighna (Anthelmintics)* because of *Tikta Rasa*. *Tikta Rasa* is best for *Raktadushti* and it removes all *Raktadushti* which is one of the major pathophysiological events in *Kushtha*.^[14]
- *Sariva*: -As *Daha* and *Vaivaranya* is one of the symptoms and sign respectively of *Kushtha Vyadhi*. *Charak* has described *Sariva* in *Dahaprasahamana (Refrigerants)* and *Varnya (complexion promoting) Mahakashaya*. It also works as *Raktapachaka* as described by *Charak*.
Manjishtha: -*Charak* has described *Manjishtha* in *Varnya* and *Vishaghna Mahakashaya* and in *Pitta Shamana Mahakashaya* by *Sushrut*. As it has *Tikta Kashaya Madhura Rasa*, It works as *Kaphapittashamaka* which gets Vitiated in *Kitibha Kushtha* and *Kushthaghna* also. In *Pachansansthana* it acts as *Krumighna*.
- *Chopchini*: *Chopchini* is *Tridoshaghna* it has *Tikta Rasa*, act as a good blood purifier (*Raktashuddhikar*) it has specific action on *Rasagranthi, Twacha* and *Snayu* also acts as *Shothahar* and *Vednashamak*
- *Karpur*: -*Karpur* has *Tikta Katu Madhura Rasa* and *Sheeta Veerya*. It does *Kapha Shamana* by *Tikta Rasa* does *Vata Shamana* by *Madhura Rasa* and *Pitta Shamana* by *Sheeta Veerya*. So it acts as *Tridoshaghna Karpur* is good

local anesthetics, dilates blood vessels and promotes sweat glands to produce sweat and hence acts as *Swedajanan* and *Dahaprasahamana*.

- *Yashtimadhu*: -Charak has described *Yashtimadhu* in *Varnya Kandughna Mahakashaya* it has *Madhura Rasa*, *Madhura Vipak* and *Sheeta Veerya*. So it is good *Vatapittashamak* and *Dahashamaka*, *Varnya* and *Kandughna*.
- *Swayambhuv Guggul*:- as the patient was complaining of *Ansa-Sandhi Shoola* (shoulder joint pain) to reduce pain as well as *Kushthagna* properties *Swayambhu Guggul* is used. *Swayambhu Guggul* is described by *Bhavprakash* in *Kushtha Vyadhi*. *Swayambhu Guggul* reduces *Kapha Dosha* and then pacifies *Vata Dosha* it also has digestive action on *Ama* and helps to reduce *Ama dosh* formation. *Swayambhuv Guggul* has *Bavachi* as its main content. *Bavachi* acts as good *Kaphavatashamak* by its *Ushna Veerya*. It also acts as *Kushthaghna*, *Jantughna*, *Vran Shodhana* and *Vranropak*
- *Rasaapachak*: -As *Samprapti* of *Kushtha Vyadhi* starts- with *Rasa* ie *Twaka* so to inhibit the progression of *Samprapti* *Rasaapachak* is used. It contains *Indrayava Patol* and *Kutaki*. *Charak* has described *Indrayava* in *Kandughna* (anti-pruritic) *Mahakashaya*. It also acts *Vranropak* (healing agent) locally. *Patol* acts as *Raktaashodhak* and *Shothahar*.
- *Rasaamanikya Rasa* - *Rasaamanikya Rasa* has Arsenic as its main content. Arsenic has good *Mamspachak* as well as *Medopachak* action. It also removes *Twaka* and *Raktadushti* and also removes *Krumi* along with *Mala*. Along with *Kushtha*, it also works good in other skin diseases like *Visarpa*, *Vipadika*, *Vicharchika* etc.⁽²²⁾

5. Conclusion

With the help of both *Shodhana* and *Shamana Chikitsa* patient got relief. Clinically patient 70% improved.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

This work is not published anywhere. The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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